
Free Translated Passages as Precursor in Enhancing the Reading Comprehension Level of Grade Nine Learners

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ABSTRACT: Reading comprehension is among the essential reading skills students must acquire before advancing to the next stage of their education in the current technological era. Despite its importance, many students still struggle with the said macro skill. This study utilized a pre-experimental research design, specifically a group pre-test and post-test research design, to examine further the effect of the Free Translated Passages using the Free Translation Method as a guide to uncover possible improvements in the reading comprehension level of the Grade 9 learners under frustration level. The content-validated and adapted-modified instrument was administered in every class discussion of each topic. Scores from 30 students were analysed using a paired sample t-test to determine the significant differences in reading comprehension levels before and after the intervention.

The results revealed that the Free Translated Passages using the Free Translation Method had both positive and negative impacts on the components of the students' reading comprehension. These concluded that the Free Translated Passages using the Free Translation Method had significantly improved students' vocabulary, literal comprehension, and inferential comprehension. However, in terms of inferential comprehension, more practice and drills are expected to be executed to help them improve in inferencing. Hence, administration and teachers of secondary schools may consider the use of other Free Translated Passages using the Free Translation Method to also improve students' other reading comprehension components. They may also employ other ways of crafting a new set of passages that students might be more interested and engaged in reading.

KEYWORDS: Free Translation Method, Reading Comprehension, Vocabulary, Literal Comprehension, Inferential Comprehension

INTRODUCTION

Reading comprehension is among the essential reading skills students must acquire before advancing to the next stage of their education in the current technological era.

Son & Tinapay et al. (2022) coined the concept of Muijselaar et al. (2017) that reading and writing are two essential skills a learner should acquire. Most academic educations base the educational and life success essentials on reading, reading comprehension, speaking, and counting. Enhancing literacy is the primary focus of the Department of Education to augment the proportion of autonomous readers among Filipino students (DepEd, 2020). It was anchored on its signature program, "Every Child a Reader," which aims to help Filipino students become proficient readers and writers at their reading level.

Adrianatos (2019) noted that educational system graduates have departed for decades without understanding what they have read, despite text comprehension being crucial for success. Reading is one of the functions of academic literacy.

Domingo and Casanova (2022) stated that, as a macro skill, reading is essential for everyone, especially students, to foster. However, based on the Program for International Student Assessment (PISA), Filipino students garnered the following scores: 353 in Mathematics, 357 in Science, and only 340 in Reading (Domingo & Casanova, 2022). These results indicate that the Philippines' educational system must address a significant issue in learning areas.

According to the 2018 PISA, the Philippines performed poorly in literacy and ranked second-worst in Mathematics and Science (Mocon-Ciriaco, 2019). The results provided allowed for identifying the reading performance difficulties encountered by Filipino students.

In high schools in the Philippines, students have a low command of vocabulary and recollection of specifics, considered fundamental (easiest) reading skills (Imam et al., 2014). According to Cabarda (2015), most students had a frustrated reading proficiency level for silent reading while they were at the instructional level for oral reading.

Students' low reading comprehension levels are linked to their poor academic performance on a deeper level. A recent study by Van den Broek and Risdan et al. (2020) examined the association between Grade 2 pupils' Reading Comprehension and

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Performance. The study found that reading comprehension significantly predicted academic performance, even after controlling for factors such as intelligence and vocabulary.

According to Guthrie and Wigfield et al. (2014), students with higher literacy levels tend to have higher academic achievement. Additionally, the researchers discovered that reading-motivated students tend to perform better academically.

Meanwhile, Francisco and Madrazo's (2019) research corroborated these ideas by establishing a strong link between academic performance and reading comprehension among students. Additionally, the researchers' study revealed that high school students in the Philippines have lower reading comprehension than the national average. The study suggested that insufficient reading materials, limited access to literature, and inadequate reading habits could be among the underlying factors contributing to the low levels of reading comprehension observed among Filipino students.

These studies suggest that interventions and strategies are required to enhance the reading comprehension of Filipino pupils, especially in elementary and secondary institutions.

In recent years, there has been a growing demand for investigating innovative teaching strategies to improve students' reading comprehension. Various studies have examined the efficacy of using translation to enhance reading comprehension. For instance, Ismail et al. (2017) found that translation could enhance students' literacy skills. Similarly, Mahmoudi (2017) discovered that translation could effectively improve the reading comprehension abilities of Iranian EFL learners.

However, despite the numerous studies conducted by many scholars, no specific research has focused on using the free translation method to enhance the reading comprehension level of frustrated readers.

Given these findings, it is worthwhile to examine further the effect of the Free Translated Passages using the Free Translation Method as a guide to uncover possible improvements in the reading comprehension level of the Grade 9 learners under the frustration level. This study aimed to determine whether the Free Translated Passages using the Free Translation Method can improve the participants' reading comprehension using passages. This study's findings could significantly impact language instructors pursuing effective strategies to enhance their students' reading comprehension.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The reading comprehension level of Grade 9 learners is a critical factor in their academic success across various subjects. However, many students struggle to grasp the meaning of texts, especially those written in a language that is not their first language. This challenge is often compounded by the limited availability of learning resources that cater to their specific linguistic needs. Given this context, exploring alternative methods to support learners in improving their reading comprehension skills is essential.

This study aimed to investigate the effectiveness of using English-to-Filipino passages translation (Free Translated Passages using the Free Translation Method) as a guide in enhancing the reading comprehension level of Grade 9 Frustration readers. Specifically, the study seeks to answer the following questions:

1. What are the pre-test scores of the Grade Nine students in terms of Vocabulary, Literal Comprehension, and Inferential Comprehension?
2. What are the post-test scores of the Grade Nine students in terms of Vocabulary, Literal Comprehension, and Inferential Comprehension?
3. Is there a significant difference in the pre-test and post-test scores of the students before and after the exposure to the Free Translated Passages using the Free Translation Method in terms of Vocabulary, Literal Comprehension, and Inferential Comprehension?

By addressing these questions, the study contributed to understanding how language accessibility through translation can improve educational outcomes in reading comprehension.

METHODOLOGY

This study employs a descriptive research design to analyze the data comprehensively. A quasi-experimental design is also implemented, involving pre-tests and post-tests for the controlled groups of Grade Nine Learners under the frustration level. This approach allows for a robust examination of the intervention's impact on students' reading comprehension levels in terms of literal comprehension, vocabulary, and inferential comprehension.

The respondents of this study were all Grade nine students from San Pablo City Integrated High School in San Pablo City who have been identified as having a reading level of frustration. This specific group is targeted to understand and address their reading challenges, providing insights crucial for developing effective educational interventions. The primary research instruments used in this study are reading comprehension pre-test and post-test assessments and passages that contain questions focusing on literal comprehension, vocabulary, and inferential comprehension. The pre-test and post- test assessments, using passages/stories, are designed to measure changes in reading levels before and after the intervention. These instruments provide quantitative data, enriching the study's findings.

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Data for this study were systematically collected through the administration of pre-tests and post-tests designed to measure the participants' reading comprehension levels before and after exposure to the intervention. These assessments utilized carefully selected and translated passages—narrative stories that were adapted from English to Filipino using the Free Translation Method. This method ensured that the translated materials retained cultural and contextual relevance, promoting accessibility and understanding among frustration-level readers. The use of familiar vocabulary and culturally appropriate contexts aimed to eliminate linguistic and comprehension barriers that students often face when reading English texts. To initiate the data collection process, the researcher formally secured approval by submitting a letter to the school principal, respectfully requesting permission to conduct the study and involve selected Grade 9 learners as respondents. Upon receiving approval, the researcher coordinated with the English teacher to incorporate the Free Translated Passages into the students' regular classroom instruction. These passages were embedded into the daily lessons to create an authentic, consistent learning environment that supported gradual improvement in comprehension skills.

The administration of the pre-tests occurred prior to the intervention period and served to establish a baseline of each student's reading performance across three key areas: vocabulary, literal comprehension, and inferential comprehension. Following several weeks of structured exposure to the translated materials during classroom discussions, a post-test was administered to evaluate the development of students' reading abilities.

Throughout the data collection process, all results were handled with strict confidentiality and care to protect the identities and academic performance of the participants. The researcher ensured that all data were stored securely and used solely for the purposes of this study. This comprehensive and ethically sound data-gathering procedure contributed to a more accurate and meaningful assessment of the impact of Free Translated Passages on the reading comprehension of the targeted learners. It also provided valuable insights into how language translation strategies can be integrated effectively into instructional practices to support struggling readers. The primary aim of this study is to evaluate and analyze the effectiveness of Free Translated Passages, translated using the Free Translation Method, in enhancing the reading comprehension levels of Grade 9 learners who are identified as frustration-level readers. Specifically, the study seeks to determine whether the integration of culturally and contextually relevant translated materials significantly improves learners' understanding of texts, particularly in the areas of vocabulary acquisition, literal comprehension, and inferential comprehension. The Free Translated Passages were strategically employed as instructional materials during daily class discussions to scaffold reading comprehension and provide linguistic support to students struggling with English texts.

To assess the impact of the intervention, a quantitative approach was employed using two primary statistical tools: the paired sample t-test and the frequency distribution test. The paired sample t-test was used to determine whether there were statistically significant differences between the students' performance before and after the intervention. This test is appropriate for measuring changes in the same group of participants across two conditions—pre-intervention and post-intervention—and allows for determining the effectiveness of the treatment, in this case, the use of Free Translated Passages.

In parallel, frequency distribution was used to identify the number of students falling under various levels of reading comprehension (Independent, Instructional, and Frustration) based on their pre-test and post-test scores. This analysis provides a clearer picture of how students' performance shifted over time and highlights the practical impact of the intervention at an individual level.

The pre-test scores served as baseline data, representing the learners' initial reading comprehension levels before they were exposed to the intervention. These scores provided critical insights into the specific areas where students were struggling and helped to establish a foundation for comparison. Following the administration of the intervention across several weeks, post-test scores were collected to measure any gains or changes in reading comprehension. These scores reflected the learners' progress and demonstrated whether the Free Translated Passages had a significant effect on improving their ability to understand written texts.

By comparing the pre-test and post-test data, the study was able to quantify the effectiveness of using Free Translated Passages in instructional settings. The results derived from the statistical analyses served as a basis for drawing conclusions about the success of the intervention and provided empirical evidence to support the potential integration of Free Translation strategies in secondary education. This approach not only contributed to assessing student growth but also offered recommendations for educators seeking to enhance reading comprehension through accessible, inclusive, and culturally sensitive instructional methods.

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RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1: Pretest Scores of the Respondents Before the Exposure to Free Translated Passages using the Free Translation Method in terms of Vocabulary, Literal Comprehension, and Inferential Comprehension

Score Range	Vocabulary		Literal Comprehension		Inferential Comprehension		Reading Comprehension Level
	F	%	F	%	F	%	
90 to 100		0	1	3		0	Independent
75 to 89	4	13	5	17		0	Instructional
75 below	26	87	24	80	30	100	Frustration
Total	30	100	30	100	30	100	

Note: Reading Comprehension level is based on the score ranges: 90-100% = Independent reader; 75-89% = Instructional reader; and below 75% = Frustration reader

Table 1 presents the pre-test scores of Grade Nine students in Vocabulary, Literal Comprehension, and Inferential Comprehension, which revealed significant challenges in their reading comprehension skills. Based on the results, most students are performing at the Frustration Level, which implies a concerning issue for their overall academic progress. As stated by Adrianatos (2019), educational system graduates have departed for decades without understanding what they have read, despite text comprehension being crucial for success; thus, the current status should be given much attention by language teachers. This was also highlighted in a more profound sense as the Organization's Program for International Student Assessment (PISA) 2022 results showed that Filipino students still have trouble understanding texts. Meanwhile, in Vocabulary, eighty-seven percent (87%) of students scored below 75, indicating a substantial gap in their word knowledge and usage. This result shows that there really is a deficiency that hinders their ability to understand and engage with texts effectively. Due to their limited repertoire of words, students find it difficult to understand the text, which is crucial for inferential comprehension. Nagy and Townsend (2018) emphasized that vocabulary knowledge is crucial for reading comprehension as it directly impacts the ability to infer meaning from context and understand complex texts. The high percentage of students at the Frustration Level suggests that we need targeted interventions to improve their vocabulary skills. This notion also finds support from Imam et al., (2014) ideas that Filipino high school students lack vocabulary and specificity, the most straightforward reading abilities and that students have low command of vocabulary and recollection of specifics, considered to be fundamental reading skills, Imam et al., (2014).

In Literal Comprehension, eighty percent (80%) of students scored below 75, which means that they struggle with basic comprehension tasks such as identifying main ideas and details. Students find it challenging, especially when they are not well-versed in the words that are crucial in identifying and recalling the literal ideas presented in the text. This notion is similar to the findings from the National Assessment of Educational Progress (NAEP) 2022 report, which highlighted a decline in reading scores among students, particularly in literal comprehension. The concept also emphasizes the need for instructional strategies that focus on improving students' ability to extract and recall information from texts. This was also supported by Dimaano and Huong (2019) that teachers should give more language exercises to address the students' deficiencies and build intervention measures based on basic comprehension.

In Inferential Comprehension, it can be gleaned that one hundred percent (100%) of students scored below 75, which is alarming. It can be inferred that students are unable to make inferences, draw conclusions, or predict outcomes, which are critical skills for higher-order thinking and academic success, since inferential comprehension is a higher-level cognitive process that is often challenging for students with limited vocabulary and literal comprehension repertoire (Kintsch, 2019).

Moreover, recent studies have shown similar trends in reading comprehension challenges among students. The NAEP report highlights the decline in reading scores among students, particularly in literal comprehension, and underscores the need for effective instructional strategies to address these gaps.

Additionally, the outcomes implied that developing the vocabulary and literal comprehension should also be addressed first, as Nagy and Townsend (2018) emphasized the importance of vocabulary knowledge in reading comprehension and suggested that we should integrate vocabulary instruction into content-area teaching to enhance students' understanding of academic texts. Kintsch's research on inferential comprehension provides insights into the cognitive processes involved in making inferences and suggests that improving students' vocabulary and literal comprehension skills can enhance their inferential comprehension abilities.

Nevertheless, these results also showed that one key factor of the students' failure in some aspects of learning might be the effect of low reading comprehension level in terms of vocabulary, literal comprehension, and inferential comprehension they are

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classified as pointed out by Van den Broek and Risden et al. (2020) that students' low reading comprehension levels are related to their poor academic performance on a deeper level.

Table 2: Posttest Scores of the Respondents Before the Exposure to Free Translated Passages using the Free Translation Method in terms of Vocabulary, Literal Comprehension, and Inferential Comprehension

Score Range	Vocabulary		Literal Comprehension		Inferential Comprehension		Reading Comprehension Level
	F	%	F	%	F	%	
90 to 100	11	37	27	90	1	3	Independent
75 to 89	16	53	2	7	9	30	Instructional
75 below	3	10	1	3	20	67	Frustration
Total	30	100	30	100	30	100	

Note: Reading Comprehension level is based on the score ranges: 90-100% = Independent reader; 75-89% = Instructional reader; and below 75% = Frustration reader

Table 2 presents the post-test scores of Grade Nine students in Vocabulary, Literal Comprehension, and Inferential Comprehension, which show significant improvements compared to their pre-test scores. The data indicates a positive shift in students' reading comprehension skills, with many moving from the Frustration Level to higher levels of comprehension. It can be gleaned that students garnered higher scores on their vocabulary, literal comprehension, and inferential comprehension questions after their exposure to the free translated passages, which were incorporated into their daily discussions. The sudden increase in their scores showed that translated passages may open new ways to improve their vocabulary, literal comprehension, and inferential comprehension skills. The notion finds support from Ismail et al. (2017) and Mahmoudi (2017) ideas that translation could enhance students' literacy skills and could effectively improve the Reading Comprehension abilities of the students. The role of translation in education is also crucial, as it aids in language learning and promotes cultural literacy (Corina, 2021).

In Vocabulary, thirty-seven percent (37%) of students scored between 90 to 100, and 53% scored between 75 to 89, leaving only 10% below 75. Despite a few numbers of students still under frustration level, it can be derived that there are students who have shown awareness to the new words and added them to their word banks through integrating them in the day-to-day discussions/communications. Based on the results, students have a better chance of improving their vocabulary skills when they have understood the meaning of an English word translated into their native language. The idea finds support from Nagy and Townsend (2018), who highlighted the vocabulary instruction integrated into content-area teaching that can significantly improve students' understanding of academic texts. Huang (2023) also emphasized the significant benefits of incorporating translation into language learning, noting that it can enhance vocabulary acquisition, reading comprehension, and writing proficiency among second-language learners. By engaging in translation tasks, learners are exposed to a broader range of vocabulary and syntactic structures, which deepens their understanding and use of the target language.

In Literal Comprehension, ninety percent (90%) of students scored between 90 to 100, and seven percent (7%) scored between 75 to 89, with only three percent (3%) below 75. The results implied that students have crafted their own ways or techniques to better understand the explicit meaning of texts as well as developing their familiarity to the words and other concepts to better recall and understand such texts. According to Jubran (2023), cross-translation aids in comprehension, increases sensitivity to language differences, and facilitates the rapid and accurate re-expression of ideas. The National Assessment of Educational Progress (NAEP) 2022 report emphasizes the importance of instructional strategies that focus on improving students' ability to extract and recall information from texts.

In Inferential Comprehension, three percent (3%) of students scored between 90 to 100, thirty percent (30%) scored between 75 to 89, and sixty-seven percent (67%) scored below 75. While there is still a significant percentage of students at the Frustration Level, students were able to reassemble their understanding of the text, connecting it to their stock knowledge, which helped them to make inferences based on the text. Students have also learned to get out of the context and guess what possible outcome may arrive using their learning and understanding of words and the literal meanings they are familiar with or have experienced. The notion also adheres to Bastola (2023), who argues that translation helps students theorize and internalize intricate ideas, providing them with the skills necessary for in-depth language analysis. Translating theoretical texts allows students to dissect and reassemble concepts to deepen their understanding and hone their critical thinking abilities. By translating these complex materials, students can bridge the gap between abstract theories and practical applications, enhancing their language pedagogy competence. The progress shown in the post-test results suggests that efforts to improve students' vocabulary and literal comprehension skills have positively impacted their inferential comprehension abilities.

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In terms of the use of the free translation method, it can also be gleaned in Dipunudun & Tan's (2023) study, which highlights how English-translated literature profoundly impacts students' reading comprehension, vocabulary, and grammar proficiency. Their study underscores the potential of culturally relevant translated texts to bridge linguistic gaps, allowing students to connect with the material more deeply. By translating texts into a familiar language, students can better grasp the nuances of English, enhancing their overall language proficiency.

Similarly, Novita and Mustafha (2019) demonstrated that translation can be an effective pedagogical tool, particularly in the context of English. The ideas are supported by the NAEP report, which highlights the importance of effective instructional strategies in improving reading comprehension skills. Nagy & Townsend (2018), and Kintsch's (2019) along with the NAEP 2022 reports emphasized the role of vocabulary knowledge in reading comprehension as well as the inferential comprehension which provides insights into the cognitive processes involved in making inferences and suggests that improving students' vocabulary and literal comprehension skills can enhance their inferential comprehension abilities.

Table 3: Test of Difference in the Pre-test and Post-test Scores of the Respondents before and after the exposure to the Free Translated Passages using the Free Translation Method in terms of Vocabulary, Literal Comprehension, and Inferential Comprehension

	Pretest		Posttest		t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
	M	SD	M	SD			
Vocabulary	5.6	1.522	8.33	0.758	10.25	29	0.000
Literal Comprehension	6.27	1.337	9.37	0.765	12.596	29	0.000
Inferential Comprehension	4.13	1.042	7.17	0.834	13.342	29	0.000

*Note: If p-value (Sig.) < 0.05, it is statistically significant
If p-value (Sig.) > 0.05, it is NOT statistically significant*

Table 3 presents the post-test scores of Grade Nine students in Vocabulary, Literal Comprehension, and Inferential Comprehension show significant improvements compared to their pre-test scores. It can be extracted from the data that a positive shift in students' reading comprehension skills, with many moving from the Frustration Level to higher levels of comprehension (Instructional and Independent levels) is evident. Among the reading comprehension skills, it can be distinguished that literal comprehension has the most significant development of pre- and post-test results as compared to other skills. This difference is influenced by various factors, including cultural context and the nature of the language being processed. While literal meanings are foundational in understanding language, their role can vary depending on the context and type of language, such as figurative expressions. (Ronderos & Falkum, 2023).

The sudden increase shows that incorporating translation into reading classrooms improves students' comprehension and enhances their reading speed and cognitive level. By using the translated texts, students can process information more deeply, improving cognitive abilities and comprehension (Zhang, 2023).

Moreover, the analysis of the pre-test and post-test scores using the Free Translation Method shows a significant improvement in students' performance in Vocabulary, Literal Comprehension, and Inferential Comprehension. The paired samples t-test results indicate that the differences in scores are statistically significant, with p-values less than 0.05 for all three areas.

In Vocabulary, the mean post-test score is 8.33 (SD = 0.758) compared to the mean pre-test score of 5.6 (SD = 1.522), with a t-value of 10.25 and a p-value of 0.000. This significant improvement suggests that the Free Translation Method effectively enhanced students' vocabulary skills. This finding emphasizes that vocabulary instruction integrated into content-area teaching can significantly improve students' understanding of academic texts.

In Literal Comprehension, the mean post-test score is 9.37 (SD = 0.765) compared to the mean pre-test score of 6.27 (SD = 1.337), with a t-value of 12.596 and a p-value of 0.000. This significant improvement indicates that students have developed a better ability to understand the explicit meaning of texts. Based on the results, there is also an importance of instructional strategies that focus on improving students' ability to extract and recall information from texts. The post-test results suggest that such strategies have been successfully implemented.

In Inferential Comprehension, the mean post-test score is 7.17 (SD = 0.834) compared to the mean pre-test score of 4.13 (SD = 1.042), with a t-value of 13.342 and a p-value of 0.000. This significant improvement suggests that students have developed better inferential comprehension skills. The outcomes indicate that inferential comprehension is a higher-level cognitive process that can be challenging for students. The progress shown in the post-test results suggests that efforts to improve students' vocabulary and literal comprehension skills have positively impacted their inferential comprehension abilities.

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Furthermore, in Vocabulary, thirty-seven percent (37%) of students scored between 90 to 100, and fifty-three percent (53%) scored between 75 to 89, leaving only ten percent (10%) below 75. This shows that students have advanced and widened their vocabularies through exposure to the words used in the passages. This also suggests that targeted interventions and instructional strategies have taken part in students' vocabulary knowledge development. Nagy and Townsend (2018) also highlighted in their study that vocabulary instruction integrated into content-area teaching can significantly improve students' understanding of academic texts.

In Literal Comprehension, ninety percent (90%) of students scored between 90 to 100, and seven percent (7%) scored between 75 to 89, with only three percent (3%) below 75. This dramatic improvement indicates that students have developed a better ability to understand the explicit meaning of texts.

In Inferential Comprehension, three percent (3%) of students scored between 90 to 100, thirty percent (30%) scored between 75 to 89, and sixty-seven percent (67%) scored below 75. While there is still a significant percentage of students at the Frustration Level, the improvement from the pre-test scores is notable. This indicates that inferential comprehension is a higher-level cognitive process that can be challenging for students. The progress shown in the post-test results suggests that efforts to improve students' vocabulary and literal comprehension skills have positively impacted their inferential comprehension abilities.

Overall, the significant differences in pre-test and post-test scores indicate that the Free Translation Method effectively improved students' reading comprehension skills. This study contributes to understanding how language accessibility through translation can enhance educational outcomes in reading comprehension. The use of translated passages in educational settings offers a range of benefits that extend beyond mere language acquisition. Translated passages can be a powerful tool in language education by improving reading comprehension, vocabulary, and cognitive abilities. Whether through traditional methods or the incorporation of technology, translation helps students engage more deeply with texts, ultimately leading to better learning outcomes. However, to fully realize these benefits, it is essential to adopt a balanced approach that includes both translation and extensive reading practices.

Based on the given findings, it can be gleaned that adjustments are also important, as Zhmayeva and Petrunenko (2020) also emphasize the importance of readdressing translation strategies to make texts more accessible to younger audiences while maintaining the genre and worldview of the original. This approach highlights the balance that must be struck between fidelity to the source text and the need to adapt it for comprehension by different readers.

CONCLUSIONS

Based on the findings of the study as summarized, the following conclusions were drawn:

- (1) There is a significant difference in the performance of the students before and after the exposure to Free Translated Passages using the Free Translation Method. Thus, the null hypothesis is rejected.

RECOMMENDATIONS

In light of the findings and conclusions, the following recommendations were presented:

1. Free translated passages using the Free translation Method, as material for intervention, may be utilized and promoted by teachers and administrators of secondary schools.
2. Teachers may use other ways to manipulate the level of context-embeddedness, localization, and cognitive demands of the passages. They may craft passages to suit the interest of the students as well as their familiarity with the topics. Such localized materials would help them further understand the text/passages they are reading.
3. English and Filipino teachers may employ the use of the passages applying the other translation method and have it validated to increase the reading comprehension level of the students. They can also use it to other advanced or independent readers as part of the Catch-up Fridays as imposed by the Department of Education (DepEd).
4. Students may also be given other books that contain translated versions, as well as tasks to listen to podcasts and English movies with subtitles to further enhance their inferential comprehension level.
5. Conducive reading areas/classrooms/library with air-conditioned machines, and other related materials may also be established for learners to practice the drill and improve their vocabulary and comprehension levels.
6. Conduct regular diagnostic assessments to track students' progress and adjust teaching strategies accordingly.
7. Provide professional development workshops for teachers on effective strategies for teaching inferential comprehension.
8. Develop a structured reading intervention program that incorporates differentiated instruction based on student performance levels.
9. Future researchers may consider the results of the respondents as a variable to further evaluate how effective the Free Translated Passages using the Free Translation Method at improving students' vocabulary and comprehension. They may also investigate the long-term impact of the passages, as well as using the other translation methods. Further research about the recall success rate after a long lapse may be a good topic to explore.

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